

AWARENESS OF NAVOI IS SELF-AWARENESS

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Abstract

This article talks about the importance of the works of Alisher Navoi, who left an indelible mark on Uzbek literature. The importance of his books in today's life is also discussed in this article.

Key words: Khamsa, theology, Hayrat-ul-Abrur.

The name of our great-grandfather Alisher Navoi is dear to all of us. For more than five centuries, the great thinker's creativity, poems inspired by the high spirit of humanism, epics, and prose works promoting high moral qualities have captivated millions of fans, and his exemplary life has become an epic in languages. His work is entirely focused on the education of society. Beautiful in form, profound in content, and highly artistic, he voiced the idea of a perfect human being. In his works, from an ordinary citizen to a king, whether he is a farmer, a student, a craftsman, a merchant, a palace official, a prince, or a sultan, he gives detailed advice on how to behave in life, what morality is, what qualities one should possess, what principles one should rely on in serving the nation and the state. Especially the education of young people is very important. The relationship of young people with society, parents, learning, and values has always been the focus of the great poet's attention. These teachings are still relevant today.

Alisher Navoi is a brilliant person who occupies a special place in the history of world civilization as an important representative of the Eastern Renaissance. He is a great poet and thinker who has made a unique contribution to the development of human thought with his humanist ideas, artistic and philosophical views, and immortal poetic works. His literary heritage is extremely large and rich. The "Khamsa", which consists of five epics, shows how high his genius was. His epics and odes, scientific and instructive works have remained relevant for centuries, even today. It would not be an exaggeration to say that such a poet who created nearly 20 genres of Eastern literature is rare in world literature. To make man mature, perfect, and tolerant in all respects, to ensure a peaceful and prosperous country, peace and well-being in the world, to invite different peoples to mutual friendship and solidarity, cooperation, is the main motto of the thinkers work for noble goals. His works, especially the epic "Khamsa", have become one of the unique monuments of world literature due to their artistic and philosophical influence and unique poetic artistry.

Navoi is a great poet and thinker, a great scientist and reformer, who collected in a single system the foundations of the Turkish literary language, the laws, and poetics of literary genres, unique to all Turkic peoples, created a perfect example of literary language, brought the art of rhetoric to the heights, presented to the world with both the scope and diversity of Turkish and foreign languages, and created beautiful Turkish literature, priceless in its richness of words.

His great love and pride for his nation are endless. For this reason, his works are read with love all over the Turkic world, and his services in the upbringing of the nation and its recognition as a person with a high level of spirituality and culture in the world are remembered with special respect. The poet's works have been translated into many languages. Today the whole world is rediscovering Navoi. Although Navoi was born in Herat, his homeland is Uzbekistan. His Holiness Navoi devoted his life to the development of science and art of our people, the development of the country, the peaceful coexistence of the nation and the nation, and the strengthening of the power of the state. It was not for nothing that Sultan Hussein Boygaro called the nation "the pillar of the homeland, the support of the state." Navoi saw public service not for career and prestige, but as an opportunity and a means to fulfill the great task of developing science, restoring the values of the nation, and instilling universal values. Alisher Navoi established institutions of higher learning such as madrasas, calligraphy schools, historiography, poetry, theology, art, and music, which were famous in the seven climes of their time.

In fact, Navoi's works were not written for only one nation. The ideas and problems he raised are of universal importance. The great thinker always considered himself to be involved in global problems and considered it his main task to raise a perfect human being and to glorify and exalt universal values.

Just as justice and honesty, patience and patience, kindness and generosity, goodness and generosity, kindness and compassion are exalted in the works of the thinker, so too are arrogance and vanity, the vices associated with pleasure and vanity. Seeing the meaning of life only in the satisfaction of self-interest and indulging in sensual pleasures is destructive. Learning is the main way to strive for perfection. Through science, man reflects on the meaning of existence, the essence of life and the infinity of universal values and perceives the truth by living them. He is freed from the torment of personal vices, he realizes his main duty - responsibility towards the material world, the duty to improve nature and society. This responsibility and duty calls man to fight for

the dominance of good, not to remain indifferent to all political, economic, social and other processes taking place on earth, factors that threaten the fate of humanity. "Virtue is the greatest work," says Navoi. - The truth that has been proven before all the peoples of the world is that the reward of goodness is goodness. Make goodness your motto and accept it as a guarantee of eternal happiness. Goodness is the most precious gem of humanity."

His views on tolerance are also unique. In his work "Hayrat-ul-Abrur", he expressed his philosophical views on religion in a marvelous way, expressing the admiration of the heart and soul. According to Navoi, although religions are different, they are based on the worship of one God.

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